

Shed Project Canvas

1. What are we trying to make/do ?

Describe the thing you want to end up with.

Keep it simple - what will exist when you're finished?

Project Title:

2. Who is it for ?

Who will use this or benefit from it?

Be specific - think of real people, not "everyone".

3. What problem are we solving ?

What's the issue, annoyance, or gap this fixes?

If there's no problem, there's no project.

Project Deadline:

4. What will we actually do ?

Break it into a few key steps.

What needs to happen to get from idea to finished result?

5. What do we need to do it ?

List the tools, materials, skills, or help required.

What do we already have, and what's missing?

6. Who needs to be involved?

What might slow this down or stop it?

Better to spot problems early than later.

7. What could go wrong ?

What might slow this down or stop it?

Better to spot problems early than later.

8. What does success look like ?

How will you know this worked?

What does a "good result" look like in practice?

9. What's out first step ?

What can you do this week to get started?

Keep it small and achievable.

